

Public Buyers Want to Go Green – Even When It’s Hard

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Summary

1. Buyers report a generally high intention to include environmental criteria in calls for tender, across a range of procurement contexts.
2. A full-factorial, between-subjects vignette experiment uncovered how transaction properties shape public buyers’ intention to include environmental criteria in construction tenders.
3. The study finds that when situations look risky, especially where asset specificity is high, respondents report a *higher* intention to use environmental criteria in a call for tender. Risks do not deter, instead, they motivate greener calls for tender.
4. However, the findings are in line with the tenets of Transaction Cost Economics. Namely, the asset specificity of the construction work and the external uncertainty induced by the disagreement of the municipal council increase the perceived global risk.
5. Public buyers are ready and willing to use environmental criteria, even in high-risk contracts. The challenge may be to make it practically feasible to follow through on their intentions. The policy recommendation is to focus on enabling action, not changing minds.

1. Introduction

Governments increasingly deploy public procurement not only to acquire goods, services, and works, but also to advance environmental sustainability, social equality, innovation, and national security. Various labeled, the procurement of broader outcomes (Grandia & Meehan, 2017), secondary policy objectives (Lerusse & Van de Walle, 2021), or socio-economic goals (Swedish Competition Authority, 2012), this approach matters because procurement represents about a third

of government expenditure (Ortiz-Ospina & Roser, 2016) and roughly a tenth of GDP across income groups (Bosio & Djankov, 2020). Given this scale, procurement is a powerful lever for broader outcomes.

Construction work is a major source of environmental harm (United Nations Environment Programme & Yale Center for Ecosystems and Architecture, 2023). To curb its impact, public buyers increasingly embed environmental criteria in procurement documents. However, the baseline uptake of such criteria is contested and appears to vary

with definitions, the specific type of procurement document, country, and year (Grandia & Kruyen, 2020; Kozuch et al., 2022; Rosell, 2021). Organizational and individual capabilities and attitudes (e.g., Testa et al., 2012) drive the use of such environmental criteria.

Transaction properties of construction work also likely influence the use of environmental criteria, according to Transaction Cost Economics (Williamson, 1999). Hence, we analyze green public procurement to understand how buyers match environmental criteria with the transaction properties of the to-be-procured construction work.

Three questions guided our study. First, does asset specificity heighten perceived exchange risk and, if so, does that risk reduce buyers' intention to use environmental criteria? Second, do external uncertainty and transaction frequency alter these relationships? Third, do specific risks mediate the link between asset specificity and environmental criteria? The three specific risks that we tested for were adverse selection (quality problems that manifest in a market over time), holdup (conflict due to sunk costs), and maladaptation (contract specifications becoming outdated).

2. Hypotheses and Experiment

We hypothesized that buyers would be more likely to use environmental criteria when transaction properties are low, with external uncertainty and frequency interacting with asset specificity. For example, this means that buyers would rather use environmental criteria when procuring for a sidewalk while the municipal council agrees on most aspects of the sidewalk and only one sidewalk needs to be built. Buyers would be less likely to use

environmental criteria when procuring for multiple suspension bridges while the municipal council disagrees about most of aspects. Suspension bridges have a higher asset specificity than sidewalks, while disagreement in the municipal council means greater external uncertainty for the procurement project. Buying multiple works rather than one implies a higher transaction frequency.

We examine how transaction properties shape a public buyer's intention to include environmental criteria in construction tenders. To test the hypotheses, we fielded a full-factorial, between-subjects vignette experiment with U.S. procurement professionals (n = 1,850). Each respondent evaluated a construction works scenario where asset specificity, uncertainty, and frequency were randomly varied across all combinations. We placed buyers in a hypothetical situation where they must procure construction work and decide on whether to use environmental criteria.

3. Main Findings

The headline result is counter to our central hypothesis. Buyers faced with greater perceived risk report a stronger, not weaker, intention to include environmental criteria. Asset specificity increases perceived risk and also has an independent, positive association with green criteria use (Fig. 1). External uncertainty raises perceived risk. Stronger domain knowledge of public procurement is associated with a lower perceived risk. Although model fit indicates that much of the variation in intentions remains unexplained, adding respondent covariates does not meaningfully change these patterns.

This tendency is most pronounced for one-off purchases where internal stakeholders broadly agree. Here, asset-specific projects are especially likely to prompt the inclusion of environmental criteria in calls for tender. This is both due to the direct effect of asset specificity on the intention and due to the indirect effect of asset specificity raising the perceived risk, which in turn raises the intention to use environmental criteria. We did not find that adverse selection risks (future quality issues in the market for the bridge or sidewalk) and maladaptation risks (contract specifications becoming outdated) played an intermediating role. Only the holdup risk (sunk costs creating future conflict between the buyer and the contractor) played a role, but only when multiple procurements are anticipated and stakeholders agree. Then, buyers may view environmental criteria as early safeguards against sunk-cost exposure.

Robustness checks support these conclusions across alternative estimation strategies, transformed outcomes and mediators, and expanded covariate sets. Two exploratory analyses help explain why buyers lean toward using environmental criteria under complexity and risk. First, a heterogeneous-effects analysis indicates that the positive response to high asset specificity is concentrated among particular practitioner profiles, notably younger or middle-aged buyers with children and more educated, older buyers. Second, coding of open-ended responses reveals that many practitioners describe environmental criteria as a way to “get it right at the beginning,” emphasizing durability, lifecycle performance, and future proofing rather than mere compliance.

Taken together, the results align with core Transaction Cost Economics tenets that asset specificity and external uncertainty elevate

perceived risk (Williamson, 1999; Macher & Richman, 2008; Cuypers et al., 2020). However, they diverge from the expectation that buyers would not use environmental criteria under higher risk because these criteria make the procured works harder to verify and thereby potentially amplify misunderstanding among contracting parties or simply contracting risks (Dulleck & Kerschbamer, 2006; Dulleck et al., 2011). Instead, buyers appear to treat environmental criteria as safeguards, which is consistent with recent experimental findings by Bauman et al. (2024) and with theories that view contracts as reference points for managing future disagreements and renegotiation (Domingos et al., 2024). The modest effect sizes and low explained variance suggest that risk-centric reasoning is only part of the story. At the level of the transaction, the availability of workable criteria in specific product groups may play a bigger role.

4. Policy Recommendations

Public buyers do not shy away from using environmental criteria when projects are risky or complex. Asset specificity and external uncertainty heighten perceived risks, in response to which buyers report a stronger intention to include environmental criteria in calls for tender. Qualitative evidence indicates this inclination grows when buyers think in longer time horizons. A low or stalling uptake of green public procurement, therefore, is unlikely to stem from a lack of intent, but rather from obstacles to implementation. This conclusion resonates with current policy debates on obstacles to building infrastructure (Anderson, 2024; Andreessen, 2020).

Diagnose and remove practical bottlenecks through applied research.

The first option for policymakers is to commission rigorous, practice-oriented studies to identify the binding constraints on environmental criteria uptake. For example, the difficulty of formulating environmental criteria for more complicated goods, services and works may be an obstacle. Applied research may need to identify which obstacles play a role, since many seem plausible.

Create a maintained library of environmental criteria for public procurement.

Establish a European repository of tested and legally reviewed environmental criteria tailored to complex construction works and other complex goods, services or works. Given the inclination of public buyers to use environmental criteria to mitigate risks, the repository may be structured around risks, and how to contract for them. Given the varied transpositions of European Directives on public procurement, there may be nationally varied ways of mitigating risks, which a repository structure could account for.

Invest in a generative AI application that assists buyers in drafting and validating environmental criteria.

Add a generative AI functionality to the existing digital infrastructure of public procurement, such as Tenders Electronic Daily. This functionality could suggest context-specific environmental criteria, propose measurable outcomes, generate checklists, and flag ambiguity. The functionality could prompt users to provide attributes of the good, service or work that is to be procured and that are associated with particular risks, such as asset specificity. Such a system should be continuously evaluated on the quality of the generated documents, the

time-to-draft, the time-to-review, the share of calls for tender with environmental criteria, the number of submitted bids, and the dispute rates.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures

Figure 1 Findings on Uptake of Green Public Procurement

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